

The transformative power of mentorship on novice teacher success: a recent systematic literature review (2022-2024)

Beranda Yii Ping Jin¹, Mohd Muslim Md Zalli¹, Mohd Ridhuan Mohd Jamil¹, Nik Muhammad Hanis¹, Josephine Ambon²

¹Department of Educational Studies, Faculty of Human Development, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, Tanjong Malim, Malaysia

²Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Malaysia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 2, 2024

Revised May 8, 2025

Accepted May 28, 2025

Keywords:

Mentorship

Novice teacher

Resilience

Systematic literature review

Teacher retention

ABSTRACT

This study examines the transformative impact of mentorship in building resilience and enhancing success among novice teachers. By identifying effective mentorship strategies and frameworks, the research addresses critical early-career challenges, supports teacher retention, and contributes to the global aim of quality education. Using a systematic literature review (SLR) guided by preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) methodology, the study analyzed 45 articles from Scopus and ERIC databases, covering publications from 2022 to 2024. Through qualitative thematic analysis, three main themes emerged: emotional and psychological support in mentoring, mentoring models and professional development frameworks, and cultural and contextual influences on mentoring. Findings suggest that mentorship is pivotal in helping novice teachers navigate stress, improve instructional skills, and adapt to diverse school environments. Limitations include the restricted scope to select databases, potentially omitting other relevant studies. Future research could broaden the literature base and assess mentoring's long-term impacts across varied educational contexts. This study contributes to the field by highlighting mentorship's essential role in fostering resilience among novice teachers, aligning with sustainable development goal 4 (SDG 4) to promote teacher retention and educational quality.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Mohd Muslim Md Zalli

Faculty of Human Development, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris

35900 Tanjong Malim, Perak, Malaysia

Email: muslim@fpm.upsi.edu.my

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition from teacher training to full-time classroom teaching is often one of the most challenging phases in a teacher's career. Despite their enthusiasm and academic preparation, novice teachers frequently need help navigating the complexities of the teaching profession. These challenges include classroom management, curriculum development, student engagement, and school culture adaptation. Without adequate support, many early-career teachers experience overwhelming stress, leading to burnout, job dissatisfaction, and, in severe cases, early attrition from the profession [1], [2]. In this context, mentorship has emerged as a critical strategy for ensuring the successful integration of novice teachers into the educational system. Mentorship, particularly within the first few years of teaching, is a critical factor in the professional development of teachers. It provides a structured environment where novice teachers can receive guidance, feedback, and emotional support from more experienced colleagues. Numerous studies have highlighted effective mentorship's profound impact on a teacher's sense of competence, job satisfaction, and

overall resilience [3], [4]. As schools across the globe grapple with the challenge of retaining quality teachers, mentorship offers a promising solution to mitigate the risk of early-career teacher attrition [5]. The relationship between the mentor and mentee is central to the success of mentorship programs. Mentors serve as role models by sharing their expertise and experiences, fostering an environment where novice teachers engage in critical reflection on their practices [6]. The mentor's dual role as a career guide and provider of psychosocial support addresses the comprehensive needs of novice teachers [7]. This multifaceted approach helps novice teachers build confidence, develop classroom management strategies, and cultivate a professional identity. Moreover, the supportive relationship helps mitigate the isolation many new teachers feel, allowing them to connect more deeply with their school community [8]. Research into mentoring practices suggests that successful programs go beyond mere instructional guidance to include emotional and psychological support [9]. Such support systems are vital, as teaching is not only an intellectual endeavor but also an emotional one. Novice teachers must manage their emotional responses to challenges in the classroom while also addressing the diverse emotional needs of their students. With proper guidance, these pressures can become manageable. Mentorship helps novice teachers navigate these emotional demands by providing a safe space to express concerns and explore coping mechanisms [10].

Besides that, effective mentorship plays a pivotal role in enhancing novice teachers' long-term career development. Through regular feedback, mentors assist new teachers in refining their pedagogical skills and adapting to their students' dynamic needs. This targeted professional development is critical for novice teachers to become reflective practitioners who can continually improve their instructional methods [11]. By observing and discussing classroom practices with experienced mentors, novice teachers develop a deeper understanding of the complexities of teaching, thus enhancing their instructional proficiency [12]. In light of these benefits, many educational systems have incorporated formal mentoring programs to support novice teachers during the critical early stages of their careers. These programs vary in structure; some focus on one-on-one mentorship, while others incorporate peer or group mentoring models. Regardless of the structure, the success of these programs depends heavily on the quality of the mentor-mentee relationship and the level of support the school administration provides. Furthermore, mentorship programs that include continuous professional development opportunities and foster collaboration are more likely to yield positive outcomes for novice teachers [13]. Research indicates that nearly 50% of novice teachers leave the profession within the first five years of teaching, underscoring the critical need for adequate support systems, such as mentorship, to help them navigate the early challenges of their careers [14]. Despite growing recognition of the importance of mentorship in fostering novice teacher success, more research is still needed on specific mentorship strategies that significantly impact their professional growth and career development [15]. While many studies acknowledge the role of mentorship in providing both psychosocial and professional support, gaps still need to be found in understanding how these practices can be optimized to address the unique challenges novice teachers face, including classroom management, adapting to school culture, and managing workload. These challenges often lead to stress, burnout, and high attrition rates, a growing concern for educational systems worldwide.

This paper addresses these gaps by conducting a systematic literature review (SLR) using the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The study seeks to identify and analyze the key factors influencing novice teacher success within mentorship programs and explore the strategies that contribute to their professional development and long-term career retention. The PRISMA method ensures a comprehensive and systematic exploration of the literature, offering insights into how mentorship can be better utilized to support novice teachers' success and retention in the profession. The novelty of this research lies in its application of the PRISMA methodology to the study of mentorship's transformative impact on novice teacher success, providing a transparent and rigorous framework for reviewing the existing body of knowledge. By applying PRISMA, this study aims to minimize bias, enhance the quality of the literature synthesis, and offer robust insights into the factors and strategies that support novice teachers through mentoring. The findings are expected to contribute to both academic understanding and practical applications, guiding the development of teacher education programs and policies that better equip novice teachers for the profession's demands. The current systematic analysis was developed to answer the three main research questions (RQ) as: i) How do mentoring practices support the emotional resilience and stress management of novice teachers, and what are the effects on their self-efficacy and professional satisfaction? (RQ1); ii) What are the most effective mentoring models for supporting the professional growth and instructional skills of novice teachers, and how do these frameworks impact teacher retention? (RQ2); and iii) How do cultural and contextual factors shape the mentoring experiences of novice teachers, and what adaptations are necessary to meet diverse educational needs? (RQ3).

This study reaffirms the pivotal role of mentorship in supporting novice teachers as they transition from training to full-time classroom teaching. The complexities of the teaching profession, including classroom management, curriculum development, and adapting to school culture, present significant

challenges for early-career teachers. Without adequate support, many experience stress, burnout, and, ultimately, early attrition. Mentorship, mainly when structured and focused on professional and emotional development, has proven to be an effective strategy for fostering novice teacher success. By conducting a SLR, this paper sheds light on the key factors and strategies within mentorship programs that address the unique needs of novice teachers, ultimately contributing to their long-term career retention. The findings of this research are expected to inform teacher education programs and contribute to achieving sustainable development goal 4 (SDG 4), which emphasizes the importance of improving teacher quality and ensuring access to quality education for all students.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study examines the impact of mentoring on novice teachers, utilizing the SLR approach to deliver an in-depth analysis of current findings. The review process begins with identifying recent publications that explore how mentoring shapes novice teachers, emphasizing individual traits, social support networks, and the organizational context, with sources drawn from the Scopus and ERIC databases. To uphold methodological precision, the PRISMA framework is employed, systematically guiding the phases of identification, screening, eligibility assessment, data inclusion, and ultimately, the synthesis and presentation of findings in descriptive summaries.

2.2. Identification

This study followed several essential steps in the systematic review process to gather a significant amount of relevant literature. First, keywords were chosen, and then related terms were identified using dictionaries, thesauri, encyclopedias, and previous research. After creating search strings for the Scopus and Eric databases, all relevant terms were identified, as referred in Table 1. In the initial phase of the systematic review, 1,657 publications relevant to the study topic were successfully retrieved from these two databases.

Table 1. The search string used for the systematic review process

Database	Search string
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("mentoring" OR "coaching" OR "guidance" OR "tutoring" OR "professional support" OR "instructional support") AND ("novice teacher" OR "beginning teacher" OR "new teacher" OR "early career teacher" OR "first-year teacher" OR "trainee teacher")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2023) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2024)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "SOC")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE , "final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j"))
ERIC	(mentoring) AND ("novice teacher") pubyearmin:2022 pubyearmax:2024

2.3. Screening

The screening process ensures that collected materials align closely with the selected research topic, explicitly focusing on mentoring's impact on novice teachers. A critical content criterion involves organizing materials by their relevance to this impact. The list of identified papers is carefully examined to eliminate duplicates. Following an initial screening that excluded 1657 publications, 241 were selected for further review based on predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria, detailed in Table 2. This criterion prioritizes relevant sources, particularly research articles, meta-syntheses, book analyses, book series, and reviews, for providing valuable insights. An additional eight publications were subsequently excluded due to duplication.

Table 2. The inclusion and exclusion criteria

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Non-English
Timeline	2022-2024	<2022
Literature type	Journal (article)	Conference, book, and review
Publication stage	Final	In Press
Subject	Social sciences	Besides social sciences

2.4. Eligibility

In the eligibility phase, the third step of the review, 233 items were evaluated to ensure alignment with the study's inclusion criteria and research objectives. Each article's title and critical points were rigorously examined during this phase. As a result, 188 articles were excluded due to lack of relevance to the study's focus, absence of empirical data, inaccessible full-text versions, or insufficient alignment of the titles with the study's aims. Ultimately, 45 articles were retained for detailed analysis, as illustrated in Figure 1.

The transformative power of mentorship on novice teacher success: a recent ... (Beranda Yii Ping Jin)

2.5. Appraisal of quality

The quality assessment of the selected articles employed the 2018 version of the mixed methods appraisal tool (MMAT), allowing for a comprehensive evaluation across varied research designs, including quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods studies [16]. The MMAT assesses each study on critical quality dimensions, including the adequacy of statistical analyses, sampling methodologies, clarity of research questions, and the alignment between the study's objectives and the data analyzed. The assessment also considers the rigor of data interpretation and the quality of study presentation, discussion, and conclusions, ensuring that the studies meet the standards necessary for inclusion in the systematic review. To ensure a robust and reliable evaluation process, two independent reviewers conducted the quality assessment for each selected article. Each article was assessed using the MMAT criteria:

- For quantitative studies, the reviewers focused on the appropriateness of statistical methods used to analyze the data, ensuring that statistical analyses were sound and suitable for the study design.
- For qualitative studies, the reviewers assessed the clarity and focus of research questions, ensuring that the studies clearly addressed their objectives and provided meaningful insights into mentoring practices.
- Mixed-methods studies were evaluated for both the appropriateness of data integration across quantitative and qualitative components and the clarity in reporting results from both types of data.

In cases where discrepancies arose between the two reviewers' evaluations, these were resolved through discussion and consensus to maintain inter-rater reliability. The independent assessments were compared, and any conflicts were addressed through joint review and clarification. This process ensured consistency and objectivity in the quality assessment and reduced bias in the final classification. Based on the MMAT scoring system, articles were rated into four quality tiers: 25% for low quality, 50% for medium quality, 75% for above average quality, and 100% for high quality. Following this assessment, 41 articles were classified as high average quality, while the remaining 4 articles were rated as above average quality. This ensures that the final selection includes studies with solid methodological foundations and reliable findings, contributing to the rigor of the systematic review process.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the proposed searching study [17]

2.6. Data abstraction and analysis

This study adopted an integrative analysis approach to examine various research designs, emphasizing quantitative methods to identify primary themes and subthemes. Data collection began with a thorough review of 45 publications to extract content relevant to the study's objectives, as shown in Figure 1. Next, recent critical studies on the influence of mentoring on novice teachers were analyzed, focusing on their methodologies and findings. The coauthors collaborated to develop themes grounded in the evidence gathered, ensuring alignment with the study's scope. A detailed log was maintained throughout, capturing

insights, observations, and challenges encountered, facilitating a precise interpretation of the data. An essential step involved comparing initial findings to identify and address any inconsistencies in theme development. In cases of differing interpretations, discussions were held to reach a consensus. This collaborative effort was also directed at resolving discrepancies in theme formulation, leading to comprehensive refinements for consistency. As the study was completed, the themes were further refined for coherence. To ensure the validity of study outcomes, two experts in educational psychology and leadership reviewed the themes for clarity, relevance, and adequacy. Their insights led to targeted refinements, enhancing theme quality and reinforcing the study's academic rigor for reliable, accessible results.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The review identified three primary themes concerning the influence of mentorship on novice teachers: i) emotional and psychological support in mentoring; ii) mentoring models and professional development frameworks; and iii) cultural and contextual influences on mentoring. These findings, as detailed in Tables 3-5 [18]–[62], provide a thorough analysis of mentorship's impact across these dimensions, offering a nuanced understanding of how mentorship supports, frameworks and contextual factors collectively shape the experiences and professional growth of novice teachers.

3.1. General background of the selected studies

The selected research includes a total of 45 studies investigating the impact of mentorship on novice teacher success across diverse national contexts. This includes two studies on mentorship practices in China and another two in Germany. 16 studies were conducted in the United States, while eight studies investigated mentorship in Israel. Four studies concentrated on the United Kingdom, with South Africa and Turkey each represented by two studies. Additional contributions include one study each from Norway, Malaysia, Lithuania, Argentina, Brazil, Japan, Chile, Kenya, and Australia. In addition, the review covers 14 quantitative studies, 20 qualitative studies, and 11 using a mixed-methods approach (both qualitative and quantitative).

Table 3. The research article finding based on the proposed criteria of theme 1 (emotional and psychological support in mentoring)

No.	Authors	Country	Year
1	Sun and Huang [18]	China	2024
2	Burger [19]	Germany	2024
3	Kwok <i>et al.</i> [20]	United States	2024
4	Diab and Green [21]	Israel	2024
5	Boyle <i>et al.</i> [22]	United States	2023
6	Mosley and McCarthy [23]	United States	2023
7	Elyashiv and Levi-Keren [24]	Israel	2023
8	Ben-David and Berkovich [25]	Israel	2022
9	Maestranzi A. <i>et al.</i> [26]	United States	2022
10	Güler and Çelik [27]	Turkey	2022
11	Milton <i>et al.</i> [28]	United Kingdom	2022
12	Shaham [29]	Israel	2022

Table 4. The research article finding based on the proposed criteria of theme 2 (mentoring models and professional development frameworks)

No.	Authors	Country	Year
1	Washington [30]	United States	2024
2	Jacobsen and Lejonberg [31]	Norway	2024
3	Oppenheimer and Goldenberg [32]	Israel	2024
4	Cohen <i>et al.</i> [33]	United States	2024
5	Ben-Amram and Davidovitch [34]	Israel	2024
6	Flory <i>et al.</i> [35]	United States	2024
7	Daly <i>et al.</i> [36]	United Kingdom	2023
8	Burger <i>et al.</i> [37]	Germany	2023
9	Haidusek-Niazy <i>et al.</i> [38]	United States	2023
10	Akiri and Dori [39]	Israel	2022
11	Mhlaba and Rankhumise [40]	South Africa	2022
12	Kwok <i>et al.</i> [41]	United States	2022
13	Mullen and Fallen [42]	United States	2022
14	Maloch <i>et al.</i> [43]	United States	2022
15	Hope <i>et al.</i> [44]	United States	2022

Table 5. The research article finding based on the proposed criteria of theme 3 (cultural and contextual influences on mentoring)

No.	Authors	Country	Year
1	Wilkinson [45]	United Kingdom	2024
2	Svajda-Hardy and Kwok [46]	United States	2024
3	Cesário and Anunciato [47]	Brazil	2024
4	Goto and Yada [48]	Japan	2024
5	Curtis <i>et al.</i> [49]	Australia	2024
6	Rivera <i>et al.</i> [50]	United States	2023
7	Cronin [51]	United Kingdom	2023
8	Berbain <i>et al.</i> [52]	Argentina	2023
9	Mokonea and Setlalentoa [53]	South Africa	2023
10	Njenga [54]	Kenya	2023
11	Xu <i>et al.</i> [55]	China	2022
12	Rogers <i>et al.</i> [56]	United States	2022
13	Zavelevsky <i>et al.</i> [57]	Israel	2022
14	Jakavonytė-Staškuvienė and Ignatavičiūtė [58]	Lithuania	2022
15	Dikilitaş and Comoglu [59]	Turkey	2022
16	Sutton <i>et al.</i> [60]	Chile	2022
17	Sebald <i>et al.</i> [61]	United States	2022
18	Chandran <i>et al.</i> [62]	Malaysia	2022

3.2. Discussion

The objective of this study was to systematically assess the impact of mentoring on novice teachers, with a focus on fostering resilience, professional growth, and job satisfaction. Through an extensive review of 45 studies, three main themes emerged: emotional and psychological support in mentoring; mentoring models and professional development frameworks; and cultural and contextual influences on mentoring. These themes highlight how structured mentorship significantly reduces stress, promotes emotional stability, and enhances self-efficacy, providing critical support for novice teachers as they navigate professional challenges. The findings further reveal that adaptable, culturally relevant mentoring models are essential in effectively addressing the varied needs of novice teachers, contributing to their resilience and sustained commitment to the teaching profession.

3.2.1. Emotional and psychological support in mentoring

Emotional and psychological support for novice teachers within mentoring programs has become increasingly crucial in enhancing teachers' resilience and overall job satisfaction. Research by Sun and Huang [18] on rural Chinese novice teachers highlights the essential role of emotional resilience as a professional capability, enabling teachers to handle work-related emotional challenges. This study, grounded in a social-ecological perspective, identifies various factors influencing resilience, including personal resources and institutional support, which foster teachers' development through emotional stability. Likewise, research by Boyle *et al.* [22] on exploration of U.S. first-year teachers reveals that effective mentoring can mitigate stress, with mentored teachers demonstrating a notably lower risk of occupational stress than their unmentored peers. This study aligns with Diab and Green [21], who underscore the importance of formal and informal support systems in boosting resilience, particularly in diverse sociocultural contexts where emotional and psychological support can shape professional satisfaction. Constructivist mentoring approaches have also shown a profound impact on emotional management and self-efficacy among novice teachers [19]. The research, using longitudinal data from Germany, reveals that constructivist mentoring significantly enhances self-efficacy, although it has limited direct effects on emotional management.

This finding resonates with Kwok *et al.* [20], whose study illustrates that novice teachers rate their mentors' effectiveness highly when there is a strong alignment between mentoring practices and their initial beliefs. Besides that, innovative models, such as mentoring "incubators," create dual support systems that promote professional development for mentors and mentees, further contributing to the psychological stability of novice teachers [24]. Social and emotional factors significantly affect novice teachers' adaptation to diverse mentoring environments. Diab and Green [21] emphasize that support systems encompassing formal mentorship and cultural support networks enhance emotional well-being and retention among novice teachers. Similarly, Milton *et al.* [28] assert that mentoring effectiveness in Wales is contingent on the collective engagement of all school staff, not just designated mentors. This inclusive approach to mentorship, which views schools as sites of complex, relational interactions, reflects the need for holistic support mechanisms that cater to various emotional and professional needs.

Moreover, Ben-David and Berkovich [25] expand on relational mentoring, demonstrating how robust mentoring relationships in a teacher's second year contribute to improved confidence and emotional security. The presence of emotional support in mentorship programs also mitigates stress-related challenges

commonly faced by new teachers. In their analysis of the NTPS data, Boyle *et al.* [22] identified that the absence of a mentor corresponds to a higher stress risk. Complementary to this, Mosley and McCarthy [23] shows that novice teachers who perceive mentoring as frequent and helpful are more likely to experience a balance between job demands and available resources, thereby reducing stress. Sun and Huang [18] further affirm that emotional resilience in teachers is shaped by the cumulative effects of mentorship and supportive policies, which are exceptionally vital for teachers in challenging environments. E-mentoring has emerged as a modern emotional and professional support method for new teachers. Güler and Çelik [27] demonstrated that e-mentoring, through video-based lesson analysis, significantly improves novice teachers' ability to reflect and manage classroom situations, thereby reducing stress. The findings from Shaham [29] study of Israeli teachers corroborate this by highlighting the positive effects of reflective observation on new teachers' confidence and resilience. Maestranzi *et al.* [26] further emphasize the value of self-reflection in mentorship, advocating for mentors to engage in self-awareness practices to better support novice teachers' culturally responsive pedagogy and emotional needs.

3.2.2. Mentoring models and professional development frameworks

Mentoring models and professional development frameworks are essential to the retention and success of novice teachers, addressing factors such as skill acquisition, emotional support, and career satisfaction. Analyzing diverse mentoring practices globally, a consensus emerges on the need for tailored, structured, and continuous support systems. Formal mentoring programs, for example, offer structured guidance with clear role definitions and are often effective in schools with rigid administrative processes, as noted by Shaham [29]. On the other hand, informal peer mentoring complements formal systems by addressing emotional well-being and providing an immediate support network [37]. In addition, directive coaching models, such as those described by Cohen *et al.* [33], improve instructional skills and resilience when short-term, goal-oriented coaching is applied. Formal mentoring programs are highly effective in environments that require strict alignment with institutional goals, as observed in Norway's education system by Jacobsen and Lejonberg [31]. Informal peer mentoring excels in fostering emotional support, particularly in urban schools where cultural contexts and shared experiences play a significant role [34].

Case studies further illustrate the successful implementation of mentorship models. For instance, Haidusek-Niazy *et al.* [38] provide insights into the role of e-mentoring during the COVID-19 pandemic, which, when applied effectively, enhanced accessibility and continuity of mentoring relationships. Conversely, inadequate training in digital tools often led to reduced personal connection and mentoring quality. These findings highlight the importance of contextual and cultural adaptability in mentoring practices. Holistic mentoring models, as described by Ben-Amram and Davidovitch [34], integrate technical skills, emotional support, and career planning to provide comprehensive support systems, especially in challenging regions like Israel. Similarly, Mhlaba and Rankhumise [40] found that holistic mentoring approaches were effective in retaining novice science teachers in Gauteng by enhancing teaching effectiveness and addressing emotional challenges. These examples demonstrate how mentorship models can be tailored to address the unique needs of novice teachers.

To offer actionable insights for practitioners, this article recommends establishing clear role definitions, fostering cultural sensitivity, and balancing formal and informal mentoring approaches to address diverse needs. For example, systemic mentoring models, such as those described by Maloch *et al.* [43], emphasize structured feedback mechanisms and collaborative goal-setting, which ensure alignment with mentees' professional development objectives. Comparative analysis further reveals the strengths and limitations of various models. Formal mentoring ensures structure and accountability but may lack the emotional connection of informal systems. Holistic mentoring provides comprehensive support but requires significant resource allocation, as noted by Mullen and Fallen [42]. Meanwhile, directive coaching enhances immediate instructional quality but may not address long-term resilience unless combined with other models. Addressing gaps in current practices, this article proposes blending mentoring models to create adaptable frameworks that cater to individual mentee needs. For instance, combining instructional coaching with holistic support has proven effective in improving both pedagogical skills and emotional well-being. This aligns with Kwok *et al.* [41], who advocate for vertical professional development that links immediate skill acquisition with long-term career aspirations. These findings suggest practical solutions for enhancing mentorship effectiveness while bridging existing gaps in practice.

3.2.3. Cultural and contextual influences on mentoring

Mentorship practices are profoundly shaped by the cultural and economic contexts in which they are implemented. Across various regions and educational settings, there are nuanced differences that influence the efficacy and outcomes of mentoring. For instance, Xu *et al.* [55] emphasize the role of job crafting in mentoring novice teachers in China, highlighting that specific forms of task and skill crafting facilitate tacit knowledge transfer. This contrasts with findings from Wilkinson [45], who identifies a lack of formal mentor

recognition in English schools, leading to the over-reliance on informal, unstructured mentoring practices. These disparities underline the necessity of aligning mentoring approaches with cultural expectations and institutional structures to ensure meaningful support for novice teachers. In rural and resource-constrained contexts, the challenges of mentoring are particularly pronounced. Rivera *et al.* [50] investigate mentoring for special education teachers in rural U.S. schools, underscoring the value of professional learning networks and targeted support programs in mitigating isolation and burnout. Similarly, Zavelevsky *et al.* [57] advocate for integrating mentoring into Israel's Ecological School Culture Index to bolster teacher retention. Their findings reveal the critical role of collegial relationships in compensating for limited resources and fostering a collaborative environment. These examples highlight how culturally and economically tailored mentoring frameworks can address the unique challenges faced by educators in under-resourced areas.

Mentoring practices also differ significantly in how they support instructional growth across diverse settings. Sutton *et al.* [60] describe how pedagogical mentoring in Chile fosters teacher reflection and instructional quality through collaborative practices. This is echoed by Rogers *et al.* [56], who demonstrate that mentorship in the U.S. enhances novice teachers' assessment literacy, empowering them to design and interpret assessments effectively. These studies collectively point to the importance of embedding mentoring within a co-learning framework that prioritizes ongoing professional development. Frameworks for mentoring in low-resource settings offer practical strategies to overcome systemic limitations. For instance, Njenga [54] critiques the absence of structured mentorship for vocational teachers in Kenya, advocating for policy-driven initiatives to formalize mentoring practices. Similarly, Mokonea and Setlalentoa [53] explore the use of e-portfolios in South Africa, finding that structured guidance from mentors significantly enhances teacher confidence and self-efficacy. Such innovations provide scalable solutions for improving mentorship in resource-constrained environments. In diverse cultural contexts, mentorship practices often reflect unique social and institutional dynamics. For example, Goto and Yada [48] in Japan stress the importance of formative interventions tailored to the professional growth phases of novice teachers.

Meanwhile, Dikilitaş and Comoglu [59] highlight the transformative impact of mentoring on TESOL teachers across international contexts, particularly in bridging theoretical and practical gaps. These findings underscore that culturally responsive mentoring practices not only enhance professional competence but also promote teacher autonomy and satisfaction. To strengthen the utility of mentoring for educators and policymakers, it is crucial to address region-specific challenges. For instance, Berbain *et al.* [52] demonstrate how mentorship improves classroom management and relational skills among novice English teachers in Argentina, while Chandran *et al.* [62] illustrate how collegial support in Malaysia mitigates early teaching challenges. Such adaptations provide actionable insights for developing mentorship programs that are responsive to the socio-economic realities of educators in different regions. By integrating these culturally and contextually informed strategies, mentorship can become a more effective tool for building teacher resilience and fostering professional growth. This tailored approach ensures the relevance of mentoring practices in diverse and resource-constrained environments, offering actionable frameworks for educators and policymakers worldwide.

4. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the transformative role of mentorship in addressing the unique challenges faced by novice teachers, such as stress, burnout, classroom management, and adaptation to school culture. These challenges, often experienced during the initial years of teaching, highlight the critical need for effective mentorship programs to foster resilience and professional growth. Through a SLR of 45 studies conducted between 2022 and 2024, three key themes emerged: emotional and psychological support, mentoring models and professional development frameworks, cultural and contextual influences on mentoring. These findings emphasize that well-structured and culturally adaptive mentorship models are instrumental in reducing stress, enhancing instructional skills, and promoting long-term teacher retention. Despite its contributions, this study acknowledges several limitations, including reliance on Scopus and Eric databases, which may have excluded relevant studies, and potential publication bias and language constraints that limit access to non-English research. These factors may impact the generalizability of findings to diverse educational contexts. Future research should address these limitations by adopting broader database searches and incorporating non-English studies to provide a more comprehensive understanding of mentorship practices across different regions and contexts.

To provide clearer guidance for future studies, this research outlines specific recommendations. Firstly, examining the long-term impacts of mentorship on teacher retention is crucial to understanding how sustained mentorship influences career commitment and job satisfaction. Secondly, investigating the integration of digital tools, such as e-mentoring platforms, is necessary to explore their potential in enhancing mentoring practices, particularly in resource-constrained or remote settings. Thirdly, exploring mentorship's

role in fostering cultural adaptability and managing workloads is essential, especially in diverse educational settings where novice teachers often face unique challenges. These targeted areas of future research are expected to contribute significantly to the refinement of mentorship frameworks. This study offers actionable insights for policymakers and educators, emphasizing the importance of structured mentorship frameworks that incorporate both emotional and professional support. Programs that integrate digital tools and culturally responsive practices are essential to help novice teachers effectively navigate their early career challenges. Furthermore, longitudinal research is necessary to observe the evolving role of mentorship in shaping novice teachers' professional growth and its broader impact on educational outcomes. Mentorship remains a cornerstone for ensuring novice teacher resilience and professional success. By refining mentorship strategies to align with the diverse needs of early-career educators, this study contributes to achieving SDG 4, which emphasizes improving teacher quality and ensuring inclusive, equitable education for all. Future research should continue to explore innovative mentorship practices to build sustainable, supportive environments for novice teachers globally.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The generous financial support provided by the Research Management and Innovation Centre (RMIC), UPSI, is gratefully acknowledged as it has been instrumental in advancing this study.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This study did not receive any specific funding or financial support.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Beranda Yii Ping Jin	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓
Mohd Muslim Md Zalli	✓	✓				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Mohd Ridhuan Mohd Jamil	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	
Nik Muhammad Hanis		✓		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			✓	
Josephine Ambon	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓				

C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditting

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The author declares no potential conflict of interest concerning this paper's research, authorship, or publication.

INFORMED CONSENT

Not applicable. This study does not involve human participants or the collection of primary data.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

As a review of research using publicly available secondary data, this research was exempt from Human Subjects approval.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [MMMZ], upon reasonable request.

The transformative power of mentorship on novice teacher success: a recent ... (Beranda Yii Ping Jin)

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Evashkovsky and A. V. Osipova, "Understanding Novice Special Education Teachers' and Paraeducators' Mentorship Relationships: A Comparative Case Study," *The Journal of Special Education Apprenticeship*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 4, 2023, doi: 10.58729/2167-3454.1157.
- [2] B. Kutsyuruba, L. Godden, and J. Bosica, "The impact of mentoring on the Canadian early career teachers' well-being," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 285–309, 2019, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-02-2019-0035.
- [3] C. Whalen, E. Majocha, and S. van Nuland, "Novice teacher challenges and promoting novice teacher retention in Canada," *European Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 591–607, 2019, doi: 10.1080/02619768.2019.1652906.
- [4] B. Kutsyuruba, K. Walker, and L. Godden, "Creating supportive school cultures for beginning teachers: Mitigating the cultural contextual factors," *International Journal of Educational Organization and Leadership*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 1–18, 2017, doi: 10.18848/2329-1656/CGP/v24i02/1-18.
- [5] B. P. J. Yii *et al.*, "From classroom challenges to scholarly insights: A bibliometric analysis of novice teacher research," *British Educational Research Journal*, pp. 1–32, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.1002/berj.4153.
- [6] S. L. Dias-Lacy and R. V. Guirguis, "Challenges for New Teachers and Ways of Coping with Them," *Journal of Education and Learning*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 265–272, May 2017, doi: 10.5539/jel.v6n3p265.
- [7] J. S. White, P. G. Schempp, B. A. McCullick, B. S. Berger, and J. M. Elliott, "Mentoring relationships in sport from the protege's perspective," *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 152–168, Feb. 2017.
- [8] J. Sparks, R. Tsemenhu, R. Green, W. Truby, L. L. Brockmeier, and K. D. Noble, "Investigating New Teacher Mentoring Practices," *National Teacher Education Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 59–65, Jan. 2017.
- [9] J. Burger, H. Bellhäuser, and M. Imhof, "Mentoring styles and novice teachers' well-being: The role of basic need satisfaction," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 103, p. 103345, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2021.103345.
- [10] K. Poom-Valickis, "Novice Teachers' Professional Development During the Induction Year," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 112, pp. 764–774, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1228.
- [11] S. A. Nagro, S. E. Hirsch, and M. J. Kennedy, "A Self-Led Approach to Improving Classroom Management Practices Using Video Analysis," *TEACHING Exceptional Children*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 24–32, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1177/0040059920914329.
- [12] C. Lee, "An analysis of the experiences of Kindergarten Teachers Participating in Novice Teacher Education using Mentoring," (in Korean), *Korean Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 87–105, 2023, doi: 10.14333/kjte.2023.39.6.04.
- [13] R. Li, "Mentoring as a supportive way for novice teachers in foreign language teacher development: A case study in an ethnic college in china," *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 318–327, 2016, doi: 10.17507/jltr.0702.10.
- [14] A. Amitai and M. van Houtte, "Being pushed out of the career: Former teachers' reasons for leaving the profession," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 110, p. 10354, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2021.103540.
- [15] N. Dağ and M. H. Sari, "Areas of mentoring needs of novice and preservice teachers," *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 115–129, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.26822/iejee.2017131892.
- [16] Q. N. Hong *et al.*, "The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) version 2018 for information professionals and researchers," *Education for Information*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 285–291, 2018, doi: 10.3233/EFI-180221.
- [17] M. J. Page *et al.*, "The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews," *The BMJ*, vol. 372, p. n71, 2021, doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.
- [18] X. Sun and J. Huang, "Thriving or surviving? Emotional resilience development among Chinese rural beginning teachers from a social-ecological perspective," *International Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 125, p. 102359, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.IJER.2024.102359.
- [19] J. Burger, "Constructivist and Transmissive Mentoring: Effects on Teacher Self-Efficacy, Emotional Management, and the Role of Novices' Initial Beliefs," *Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 75, no. 1, pp. 107–121, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1177/00224871231185371.
- [20] A. Kwok, M. S. Patterson, M. I. Suárez, D. Huston, and D. Mitchell, "Rate your coach: exploring ratings of coaching skills throughout teacher induction," *Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 563–584, 2024, doi: 10.1080/13540602.2023.2265823.
- [21] A. Diab and E. Green, "Cultivating Resilience and Success: Support Systems for Novice Teachers in Diverse Contexts," *Education Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 7, p. 711, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.3390/educsci14070711.
- [22] L. H. Boyle, K. C. Mosley, and C. J. McCarthy, "New teachers' risk for stress: associations with mentoring supports," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 95, 2023, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-05-2022-0037.
- [23] K. C. Mosley and C. J. McCarthy, "Beginning Teacher Mentoring: Associations between Mentoring Experiences and Stress among First Year Teachers," *Teacher Educator*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 440–458, 2023, doi: 10.1080/08878730.2023.2175402.
- [24] R. A. Elyashiv and M. Levi-Keren, "The incubator: an innovative approach to professional development for beginning teachers and mentors," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 18–32, 2023, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-04-2022-0023.
- [25] H. V. Ben-David and I. Berkovich, "Functions and relational aspects of mentoring for novice teachers during the second year of teaching," *Journal of Education for Teaching*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 549–560, 2022, doi: 10.1080/02607476.2021.2017234.
- [26] A. M. Maestranzi, J. Bolgatz, N. Brown, and M. Jackson, "Exploring Tensions: A Self-Study of A Teacher Educator's White Fragility in Mentoring Novice Teachers," *Studying Teacher Education*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 40–60, 2022, doi: 10.1080/17425964.2021.1969227.
- [27] M. Güler and D. Çelik, "Supporting novice mathematics teachers: The impact of e-mentoring on lesson analysis skills," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 113, p. 103658, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2022.103658.
- [28] E. Milton, C. Daly, F. Langdon, M. Palmer, K. Jones, and A. J. Davies, "Can schools really provide the learning environment that new teachers need? Complexities and implications for professional learning in Wales," *Professional Development in Education*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 878–891, 2022, doi: 10.1080/19415257.2020.1767177.
- [29] C. Shaham, "Training for Teaching – Reflective Observation of Beginning Teachers in their First Year," *Curriculum and Teaching*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 79–99, 2022, doi: 10.7459/ct/37.1.05.
- [30] V. S. Washington, "A Case Study: A Novice Teacher's Mentoring Experiences the First Year and Beyond," *Education and Urban Society*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 309–344, 2024, doi: 10.1177/00131245221121664.
- [31] H. M. Jacobsen and E. Lejonberg, "Organizing mentoring and induction practices: understood through the eyes of newly qualified teachers," *Mentoring and Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 395–418, 2024, doi: 10.1080/13611267.2024.2360603.

- [32] O. S. Oppenheimer and J. Goldenberg, "The impact of professional mentoring on mentors of novice-teachers," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 122–141, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-08-2022-0070.
- [33] J. Cohen, V. C. Wong, A. Krishnamachari, and S. Erickson, "Experimental Evidence on the Robustness of Coaching Supports in Teacher Education," *Educational Researcher*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 19–35, 2024, doi: 10.3102/0013189X231198827.
- [34] M. Ben-Amram and N. Davidovitch, "Novice Teachers and Mentor Teachers: From a Traditional Model to a Holistic Mentoring Model in the Postmodern Era," *Education Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 2, p. 14, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.3390/educsci14020143.
- [35] S. B. Flory, R. Marttinen, C. V. Niema, and V. J. F. Lindsay "Successful Practices of Novice Urban Physical Education Teachers," *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp 510–516, 2023, doi: 10.3102/2008486.
- [36] C. Daly *et al.*, "Mentors as instructional coaches for new teachers: lessons learnt from the early career framework in England," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 350, 2023, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-10-2022-0090.
- [37] J. Burger, P. Schulz, and M. Imhof, "Patterns of formal and informal support within teacher induction–latent classes and their implications for novices' competence and well-being," *Mentoring and Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 612–634, 2023, doi: 10.1080/13611267.2023.2279892.
- [38] S. Haidusek-Niazzy, D. Huyler, and R. E. Carpenter, "Mentorship reconsidered: A case study of K-12 teachers' mentor-mentee relationships during the COVID-19 pandemic," *Social Psychology of Education*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 1269–1288, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11218-023-09788-w.
- [39] E. Akiri and Y. J. Dori, "Professional Growth of Novice and Experienced STEM Teachers," *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 129–142, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10956-021-09936-x.
- [40] R. E. Mhlaba and M. P. Rankhumise, "Mentoring novice natural science teachers: a case study in the Gauteng province," *South African Journal of Education*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2022, doi: 10.15700/SAJE.V42N1A2003.
- [41] A. Kwok, J. Keese, M. I. Suárez, D. Mitchell, and D. Huston, "Novice teacher vertical professional development? Exploring teachers' and coaches' beliefs throughout a two-year induction program," *Learning Environments Research*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 255–270, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10984-021-09360-3.
- [42] C. A. Mullen and M. S. Fallen, "Navigating Uncharted Waters': New Teacher Mentoring and Induction," *Research in Educational Administration and Leadership*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 751–785, 2022, doi: 10.30828/real.1165667.
- [43] B. Maloch, M. M. Wetzel, S. Tily, A. Daly, J. Murdter-Atkinson, and C. Krafka, "Mentoring in a University-based Induction Program," *Teacher Educator*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 431–451, 2022, doi: 10.1080/08878730.2022.2107131.
- [44] S. T. Hope, L. M. Abrams, and D. T. Marshall, "Coaching in teacher residency programs: a strategy for professional learning and development for in-service teachers," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 434–451 2022, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-11-2021-0102.
- [45] C. Wilkinson, "School-Based Teacher Mentoring – Further Evidence for the 'Cinderella' Metaphor?," *Educational Process: International Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 15–34, 2024, doi: 10.22521/edupij.2024.131.2.
- [46] M. Svajda-Hardy and A. Kwok, "First-Year Teacher Needs in the Urban Classroom: Creating a Sustainable Framework for Classroom Management Coaching," *Urban Review*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 103–121, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11256-023-00667-4.
- [47] P. M. Cesário and R. M. M. Anunciato, "Identification of training needs of early career teachers in a mentoring program*," *Educação e Pesquisa*, vol. 50, p. e273481, 2024, doi: 10.1590/S1678-4634202450273481EN.
- [48] I. Goto and T. Yada, "Exploring Mentor Teachers' Experiences and Practices in Japan: Formative Intervention for Self-Directed Development of Novice Teachers," *Open Education Studies*, vol. 6, no. 1, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1515/edu-2024-0022.
- [49] E. Curtis, H. T. M. Nguyen, E. Larsen, and T. Loughland, "The positioning tensions between early career teachers' and mentors' perceptions of the mentor role," *British Educational Research Journal*, vol. 50, no. 3, p. 1327, 2024, doi: 10.1002/berj.3974.
- [50] C. J. Rivera, B. Sasser, and J. Baker, "State-Wide Programming for Supporting New Special Education Teachers: A Rural Perspective," *Rural Special Education Quarterly*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 193–201, 2023, doi: 10.1177/87568705231201171.
- [51] S. Cronin, "Early career mentoring in England: a case study of professional discretion and policy disconnection," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 366–386, 2023, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-10-2022-0088.
- [52] M. P. Berbain, L. Payaslian, A. S. Rosas, B. G. A. L. Porta, and A. L. Porta, "The Impact of Mentoring on English Language Teachers: A Case From Argentina," *Profile: Issues in Teachers' Professional Development*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 49–64, 2023, doi: 10.15446/profile.v25n1.101711.
- [53] M. V. Mokonea and W. Setlaletoa, "Enhancing Self-Efficacy of Beginner Teachers in the Use of E-Portfolio: The Role of a Mentor Teacher," *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 130–140, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.46303/jcsr.2023.10.
- [54] M. Njenga, "TVET teacher mentoring in Kenya: valued but poorly implemented," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 113–127, 2023, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-04-2022-0028.
- [55] J. Xu, X. Wei, R. D. Hisrich, M. Yu, and X. Li, "Mentoring and Tacit Knowledge Transfer in Novice Teachers From Chinese Middle Schools: Mediating Effect of Job Crafting," *Frontiers in Education*, p. 772638, 2022, doi: 10.3389/educ.2022.772638.
- [56] A. P. Rogers, E. M. Reagan, and C. Ward, "Preservice teacher performance assessment and novice teacher assessment literacy," *Teaching Education*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 175–193, 2022, doi: 10.1080/10476210.2020.1840544.
- [57] E. Zavelevsky, P. Benoliel, and O. Shapira - Lishchinsky, "Retaining novice teachers: The meaning and measure of ecological school culture construct," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 117, p. 103783, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2022.103783.
- [58] D. Jakavonytė-Staškuvienė and L. Ignatavičiūtė, "Experience of mentors and beginner primary school teachers in applying the principles of shared leadership during the school adaptation period: The case of Lithuania," *Cogent Education*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 2070054, 2022, doi: 10.1080/2331186X.2022.2070054.
- [59] K. Dikilitaş and I. Comoglu, "Mentoring beginning TESOL teacher researchers: experiences from international contexts," *European Journal of Applied Linguistics and TEFL*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 95–112, 2022.
- [60] S. S. Sutton, C. Cuéllar, M. P. González, and M. J. Espinosa, "Pedagogical mentoring in Chilean schools: an innovative approach to teachers' professional learning," *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 69–88, 2022, doi: 10.1108/IJMCE-01-2021-0028.
- [61] A. M. Sebal, J. Howe, and M. M. Balgopal, "The impact of co-teaching on the professional practices of veteran, novice, and potential science and mathematics teachers," *School Science and Mathematics*, vol. 122, no. 1, pp. 4–15, 2022, doi: 10.1111/ssm.12508.
- [62] V. N. Chandran *et al.*, "Malaysian English Language Novice Teachers' Challenges and Support during Initial Years of Teaching," *Studies in English Language and Education*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 443–461, 2022, doi: 10.24815/SIELE.V9I2.22974.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Beranda Yii Ping Jin is a Ph.D. candidate in educational psychology at the Faculty of Human Development, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris (UPSI), Malaysia, specializing in the resilience of novice teachers. Her research explores how early career educators build resilience to cope with the unique challenges of the teaching profession, such as high demands, stress, and adaptation to diverse learning environments. She examines the influence of mentoring, support networks, and personal coping strategies on novice teachers' ability to persist and thrive, providing insights that can inform policies and frameworks designed to strengthen resilience in the early stages of a teaching career. She can be contacted at email: beranda1993@yahoo.com.

Mohd Muslim Md Zalli is a senior lecturer at the Faculty of Human Development, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris (UPSI), Malaysia. He does research in higher learning education and school setting specifically related to learners' behavior in the online courses, learning strategies, and teaching quality. He is also a member of the International Study Association on Teachers and Teaching and is actively involved as the ATLAS.ti certified trainer. He can be contacted at email: muslim@fpm.upsi.edu.my.

Mohd Ridhuan Mohd Jamil is a senior lecturer at the Department of Educational Studies, Faculty of Human Development in Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris (UPSI). He earned his Ph.D. in Engineering Education from the University of Malaya in 2016 and has over 17 years in teaching. He is an appointed MQA evaluator for engineering and education programs. Furthermore, he serves as the chairman and panel member for the evaluation of the Mechanical Engineering Studies and Engineering Drawing textbooks for Form 4 and 5 (KSSM). Actively engaged in research, he has authored three books on research methodology and two books in the field of TVET and curriculum. He has an H-index of 3 on Scopus and 16 on Google Scholar. He can be contacted at email: mridhuan@fpm.upsi.edu.my.

Nik Muhammad Hanis is a senior lecturer in the Department of Educational Studies, Faculty of Human Development, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, with expertise in Pedagogy and Andragogy. He holds a Doctor of Philosophy in Education from the International Islamic University Malaysia and is a certified professional trainer by HRD Corp, as well as a certified DISC Profile Analyst from UTM Space. With over 10 years of experience, he has conducted training programs, seminars, consultancy, and workshops for various organizations. He can be contacted at email: nik.mdhanis@fpm.upsi.edu.my.

Josephine Ambon is a Ph.D. candidate at Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM). She is studying educational management and administration. She is passionate about raising the quality of teaching and learning for teachers, their development in schools, and the roles of school heads to manage schools effectively. Her research interests lie in the school leader's competency, the teacher's quality in teaching and learning, the teacher's professional development, and leadership. She can be contacted at email: josephineanakambon78@gmail.com and p121270@siswa.ukm.edu.my.